

NAKSHBANDIY SECT IN XIV-XV CENTURIES

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It is generally recognized that the 14th-15th centuries, which were formed in the early Middle Ages and called the second Renaissance or the Timurid era, were nourished by the Renaissance of the 9th-12th centuries as a period of unique growth. It is said that the science of Islamic mysticism was accepted from Muhammad (pbuh), and in the Tariqat, his "practices" are a document. This can be based on the series of sects that still exist today. For example, the chain of Naqshbandiyya can be linked to Abu Bakr Siddiq and Ali Abu Talib. However, during the time of the Prophet (pbuh), there were no such concepts as "mysticism", "Sufi", "sect". They considered people who lived with the aim of attaining the love of the Truth, who cultivated their souls and purified their souls, to belong to this category. During this period, its theoretical or practical aspects were not distinguished.

There is no information about Sufism and Sufism in the Qur'an or hadiths. There was no need for Pirs or guardians in those times. It is enough that the Prophet (pbuh) is a messenger who shows the way to the truth and the answer to any question can be obtained directly from him. During the time of the Companions and subordinates, spiritual education and piety, doing righteous deeds were considered important duties. Tafsir, hadith, fiqh, nahv sciences developed. The various conflicts that arose after the death of the Prophet (as) created the need for the origin of Islamic sciences. Among the Islamic sciences, it is noted in the research that it first appeared in the form of asceticism with its own characteristics. This period is called "Zuhd" period according to the views of Sufism scholars. Azizuddin Nasafi in his work "Bayan al-Tanzil" states that at the beginning of Sufism, "zuhd" appeared in the form of "dieting". According to him, Hasan Basri and Fuzayl Iyaz "Huzn" added "melancholy" to zuhd. Rabiya Adaviyya and Zunnun Misri discussed "love". Sh aqiq Balkhi and his students promoted "tawakkul". Each of these views and ideas caused various arguments and debates in their own way. German scholar Annemarie Schimmel about Rabiya al-Adaviyya : "Rabiya introduced the concept of loving God to Sufism.

The 7th-8th centuries are considered the period of "Zuhd" and it is important that the qualities manifested in ascetics, their prayers of obedience, turning away from worldly possessions, and finding the approval of God in their ascetic lifestyle, attaining the happiness of two worlds, and getting rid of

suffering, are important. counted. It was distinguished from other stages of Sufism by the fact that it did not have the concepts of knowing God and reaching his presence. The dominant emotions and concepts in the lives of the ascetics were mainly fear and hope. Ascetics of this period were dominated by the concept of asceticism based on "fear". These data, which represent the diversity of views on Sufism in general, require the study of Sufism on the basis of the analysis of the views of individual Sufism scholars across time. The Naqshbandi sect and its development are no exception.

It is written in the work "Maqamoti Khoja Bahauddin Naqshband" by Muhammad Baqir: "Know that the birth of His Highness Khoja Buzurg, that is, Khoja Bahauddin, took place in the month of Muharram in the year seven hundred and eighteen. This is the century in which Azizan lived." Fakhriddin Ali Safi in the work "Rashahot aynal-hayat" in the statement "Zikr of Hazrat Khoja Bakhool Haq wad-din Muhammad (qs) known as Naqshband" it is written as follows: "Their birth dates were in the month of Muharram on the date seven hundred and eighteen (1318). The tombs of Mavlidu are located in the Orifon Palace, and the city of Bukharodin is one farsakh away. From these evidences in the sources, it is known that the auspicious time when this noble person was born was the first and very virtuous month of Muharram according to the Muslim calendar in 718 AH. Academician AA Semyonov, who studied the life path of Bahauddin Naqshband based on Persian language sources, calculated on the basis of the Wüstenfeld table and wrote that this blessed date corresponds to the period from March 5 to April 3, 1318 AD. So, Bahauddin Naqshband was born in our country in the early days of spring and began to spread the rays of goodness. Just as every seed sown on the ground in the spring gives a harvest, the whole world is enjoying the fruits of the seeds planted by this great man, that is, the fruits of the crops that sprouted from the teachings of Naqshbandiyyah created by him.

Muhammad Baboyi Samosi Bahauddin, when he noticed the expressions of Naqshband, had prophesied that because of this blessed person, Qasri Hinduvan would become Qasri Orifon. In fact, after Bahauddin Naqshband became an enlightened person, people started coming from all over the world to learn from him. This holy place became famous as the place of Orifs and was called Qasri Orifon. Muhammad Baboyi Samosi's prophecies came true, and to this day this blessed land is known as Qasri Orifon.

Hazrat Alisher Navai, the Sultan of the word estate, writes in his work "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat": "Their horse is Muhammad bin Muhammad Bukhari."

It turns out that they named this noble baby Muhammad, who was born in spring. "Muhammad" is an Arabic word meaning worthy of praise. This blessed name is in harmony with the names of our prophet Muhammad.

Bahauddin Naqshband was a shamoili: tall, wheatish, with a thick beard, fair face. His neck shined like a light, he led everyone on the right path. Outwardly, the people were with the Truth.

Bahauddin Naqshband's father was Syed Muhammad Bukhari ibn Syed Jalaluddin, who was a kimhab weaver. Their mother, Bibi Orifa Khojai, was from the generation of Khizr. Sources indicate that his parents and lineage are very pure.

Muhammad ibn Muhammad al-Bukhari Bahauddin Naqshband is one of the blessed ones written in golden letters in the jewels of history. What great merits did this breed of noblemen get to be nicknamed Naqshband?!

"Naqshband" is derived from the words "naqsh" and "band", that is, binding, and the meaning of the pattern is binding. In the beginning, this name was given according to Muhammad's profession. In the work "Maqamoti Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband" by Muhammad Baqir, it is written that Bahauddin along with his fathers engaged in the craft of tying patterns on the best cloth coming out of Bukhara at that time. About this in the source, the following words of Hazrat Khoja are quoted: "My father and I were engaged in the profession of philanthropists." According to the work "Risolai bafandagi", weavers and embroidery craftsmen honored Bahauddin Naqshband as their pir.

After Bahauddin grew up, matured, always engraved God in his heart, and reached the level of impartial work, they began to respect him as a Naqshband, that is, a person with God engraved in his heart. Bahauddin searched for the most beautiful pattern to embroider on the kimhab and realized that this is the most beautiful pattern of Allah. This Pattern should be embroidered forever, seeing that cloth, metal and other objects disappear, he came to the conclusion that the most appropriate place to embroider it is the heart. In the beginning, Bahauddin struggled to engrave Allah in his heart. Then, gradually, skill was formed in it.

Hazrat Alisher Navoi, the sultan of poetry, was able to describe the essence of the name Naqshband given to Bahoudin in the most beautiful way. The great poet dedicated the 21st chapter of his famous work "Khamsa" "Hayrat ul-Abror" to Bahoudin. In this description consisting of 30 verses, the phrase Naqsh is used 31 times in different contexts, which beautifully shows the love of the great name Naqshband.

Bahauddin Naqshband's mentors played a big role in his development. Muhammad Babayi Samosi (died 1336) was the blessed person who gave the first lessons in Naqshband and made him aware of external and internal sciences. According to Muhammad Baqir's work "Maqamoti Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband", the first student of Bahauddin Naqshband, Khwaja Alauddin Attar, narrates that Bahauddin Naqshband said: "One of the kindnesses of Hazrat Haq Subhanahu ta'ala towards this poor man was that from my childhood, the mischievous sheikh Khwaja Muhammad Babayi Samasi I visited the blessed eyes of God and they adopted me."

Alisher Navoi, the sultan of the word estate, gave information about Khwaja Bahauddin Naqshband in his work "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" and wrote: "Khwaja Muhammad Babayi Samosiydandur is the son of Khwaja Muhammad Babai."

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